

HOSPITAL SCHOOL AND HOME EDUCATION**Usnaddinova Nargiza Aleuetdin qizi**

Student of Karakalpak State University

Urazalieva Sayora Amanbay qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University

Edilbekova Hurliman Berdibek qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University

Janabaeva Maryam Ongarbaevna

Student of Karakalpak State University

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Abstract. This study analyzes the content, main tasks, principles of hospital pedagogy, hospital education, and its relevance in the modern era. The origin of the concept of hospital education, the experience of foreign countries, and the prospects for the development of this area in Uzbekistan are also considered.

Keywords: inclusive, hospital pedagogy, inpatient facility, hematology, oncology, clinical immunology, correctional-pedagogical, rehabilitation.

GOSPITAL MAKTAB VA UY TA'LIMI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot davomida gospital pedagogika, gospital talimning mazmuni, asosiy vazifalari, prinsiplari va uning hozirgi zamonda dolzarbligi tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek gospital ta'lim tushinchasining kelib chiqishi, xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi va O'zbekistonda bu sohani rivojlantirish istiqbollari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: inklyuziv, gospital pedagogika, statsionar muassasa, gematologiya, onkologiya, klinik immunologiya, korreksion-pedagogik, reabilitatsiya.

БОЛЬНИЧНАЯ ШКОЛА И ДОМАШНЕЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ

Аннотация. В данном исследовании проанализированы содержание, основные задачи, принципы и актуальность больничной педагогики, больничного образования и ее современная актуальность. Также были рассмотрены истоки концепции госпитального образования, опыт зарубежных стран и перспективы развития этого направления в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивная, госпитальная педагогика, стационар, гематология, онкология, клиническая иммунология, коррекционно-педагогическая, реабилитация.

Introduction

In the 21st century, an inclusive approach to education is increasingly penetrating everyday life. Every child, regardless of their health or physical abilities, has the right to receive a quality education. From this point of view, it is necessary to ensure that children who are forced to undergo long-term treatment in medical institutions or at home are not left out of education. To meet this need, a hospital pedagogical system is being formed. The modern education system seeks to provide equal opportunities for every child, to ensure their full development, regardless of their health, social status and place of residence. From this point of view, the issue of ensuring the right to education of children who are being treated in inpatient institutions due to long-term illnesses is gaining urgent importance.

The attention paid to young people today and the trust they place in them are a vivid example of how great our hope for the future is. And we will not be mistaken if we say that the conditions created for their quality education are practical proof of this. Large-scale reforms are being implemented in every sphere in our country. In turn, a significant part of these reforms is the reforms being implemented in the education system. One of such large-scale reforms is the resolution “On measures to introduce a system of preschool education and upbringing and general secondary education for children treated at the Center for Pediatric Hematology, Oncology and Clinical Immunology”, adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers on May 5, 2022. In accordance with the resolution, today the “Mehrli Maktaba” state educational institution has been established in our country, which aims to ensure that sick children who need long-term inpatient treatment do not lag behind in the educational process and receive education on a par with their peers, and to assist in their social adaptation. Hospital pedagogy is a form of special education intended for children treated in health institutions (hospitals). The main task of this system is to continue the educational process of sick children without harming their health, to ensure their socialization, and to provide psychological support. The first hospital schools were established in Germany at the end of the 19th century, and are now widely developed in the USA, Great Britain, France, Russia, Japan, and many other countries..

Children suffering from a disease that requires long-term treatment is an unpleasant situation not only for the children, but also for their parents. On the one hand, the deterioration of the child's health puts pressure on his psyche, on the other hand, a sharp change in the daily situation around the patient, separation from peers and the limitation of his capabilities due to the disease cause a state of depression. In childhood, a person is

strongly influenced by psychological and pedagogical factors. Correctional, pedagogical, psychological and medical work, organized taking into account the limitlessness of the growing child's organism and the internal capabilities of his brain structure, helps to reduce the child's primary disability and prevent secondary disabilities. All these are factors that prepare a child with a developmental disability to live an independent, independent life.

Social rehabilitation (restoration) and social adaptation (adaptation) of children is a painstaking work that requires not only the qualities of the soul, but also a professional approach in this delicate area, which is gradually developing with the advent of new technologies and innovations. In order to improve this area, interdepartmental studies on children with disabilities were conducted to study the state of social adaptation of children in need. In our country, favorable conditions are being created for the education and upbringing of children with disabilities and their adaptation to social life. In order to integrate them into society, and first of all, to restore their health as much as possible, work is being carried out on the basis of the "General Education Project for Children with Disabilities". This mainly involves the use of inclusive education opportunities. As a result, a deeper study of the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of organizing inclusive education, its specific capabilities, identifying problems associated with it, and substantiating aspects of effectiveness is becoming an urgent scientific problem. Because the inclusive education method creates a convenient opportunity to ensure the full participation of all children in the educational process, regardless of their mental and physical condition. In particular, it creates opportunities for children with special needs to communicate with others, grow up to be able to meet the requirements of the social environment, acquire skills to meet their daily needs, adapt to life and study in general education schools on an equal basis with healthy peers, establish friendly relations with them, master lessons on time, and approach tasks responsibly. With this in mind, this textbook aims to substantiate the specific signs of effectiveness of inclusive education, identify the necessary pedagogical and psychological approaches to establish it in the continuous educational process from the family, preschool institutions to higher education. It is worth noting that inclusive education can create favorable opportunities not only for children with disabilities, but also for children raised in families based on a healthy lifestyle, in preschool educational institutions, schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges for students with different levels of mastery of subjects. Through it, achieving positive influence of students on each other brings good results. However, sometimes the

difference between healthy children and children with disabilities is noticeable, a child with disabilities does not join his peers, is shy, is embarrassed because he cannot use his opportunities, and some are stubborn and capricious due to being raised too manly in the family, which makes it necessary to make changes in the organization of educational practices and educational services. All this makes it clear that the inclusive education process has its own complexities and places serious demands and responsibilities on teachers, class leaders, educators, and professional masters working in this area.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that hospital education is a type of education focused on the student's personality, taking into account the individual merits, abilities and capabilities of the students, based on the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process, which is aimed at forming certain knowledge, skills and qualifications, and most importantly, at forming their personality. Hospital education should create an environment in which the student considers himself a person, feels attention to himself, and can fully demonstrate his abilities.

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